

CFD Assessment of Hydrodynamic Loads on Moored Vessels during ULCV Passages

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Abstract. Ultra-large container Vessels (ULCVs) have posed significant challenges to mooring design within ports and harbors. Their large size and displacement exert considerable loads on moored vessels during passing maneuvers in channels, leading to potential damage to lines and fenders. While studies utilizing potential flow methods, such as the Rankine Method, have investigated the impact of passing ships, these analyses primarily focus on parallel configurations. However, spatial constraints within ports and the presence of buoy-anchored vessels often result in non-parallel encounters, where viscous forces play a crucial role in determining anchor loads, normally neglected by commercial mooring analysis software. This paper presents a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) methodology to assess the hydrodynamic forces acting on a moored ship subjected to passing vessels at varying relative angles. This enables the evaluation of viscous effects on mooring design. Furthermore, the paper compares the CFD results with those obtained from empirical formulations commonly employed in commercial software. A detailed verification methodology was implemented to estimate the numerical uncertainties.

Key words: Passing Ship Effects, Overset Mesh

1. Introduction

The increasing deployment of Ultra-large Container Vessels (ULCVs) has introduced significant challenges in port and harbor mooring design. Due to their substantial size and displacement, these vessels generate considerable hydrodynamic loads on nearby moored ships during passing maneuvers, raising concerns about the integrity of mooring lines and fenders. Although previous studies have employed potential flow methods, such as the Rankine method, to analyze passing ship effects, these approaches have largely been limited to parallel ship configurations. In real-world port environments, however, spatial constraints and the presence of buoy-anchored vessels often lead to nonparallel encounters, where viscous forces become a critical factor in determining mooring loads, an aspect frequently overlooked by conventional mooring analysis software.

To address this gap, this study presents a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD)-based methodology to evaluate the hydrodynamic forces acting on a moored vessel subjected to passing ships at varying relative angles. By incorporating viscous effects, this approach provides a more comprehensive assessment of mooring loads under realistic conditions. Additionally, the paper compares CFD-derived results with empirical formulations commonly used in commercial software, offering insights into their respective accuracies and limitations. A rigorous verification methodology is also implemented to quantify numerical uncertainties, ensuring the reliability of the findings. This research aims to enhance mooring design practices by improving the understanding of hydrodynamic interactions in complex port scenarios.

2. Bibliography Review

The hydrodynamic interaction between passing ships has been a subject of study since the early 20th century. Gibson (1911) is recognized for conducting some of the first experimental investigations into this phenomenon in shallow water, performing tests with various model sizes at Dundee University College.

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Building significantly on such experimental foundations, Remery (1974) carried out an extensive series of tests measuring mooring line loads. Several key findings from Remery’s work directly influenced the present study: the observation that mooring loads are proportional to the square of the passing ship’s velocity motivated the normalization of forces by velocity squared in this paper; and the discovery that mooring system stiffness considerably impacts these forces underscored that increasing mooring line pre-tensions—a common tactic in mooring design—can reduce peak loads. Furthermore, Remery (1974) provided influential plots of forces and moments versus passing ship position, a presentational approach also adopted in this research. Subsequently, Flory (2002), drawing upon the experimental results of Remery (1974) and Muga and Fang (1975), proposed equations for predicting peak interaction forces and moments, alongside a method for developing their time histories. Muga and Fang (1975) had earlier presented a methodology to calculate these forces and moments for various ship sizes and operational parameters.

Investigations into specific hydrodynamic aspects, such as free surface effects, continued with notable contributions from Pinkster (2004), who studied the influence of the free surface on passing ship interactions. In separate research, Pinkster also examined the loads on moored ships when subjected to solitary waves (Pinkster and Ruijter, 2004). Utilizing proprietary software, his studies compared results from simulations employing the double-body boundary condition (BC) against those with full free-surface modeling. A key conclusion from this work was that for open water scenarios at low Froude numbers, the double-body BC offers a reasonable approximation of the flow conditions.

More recently, significant advancements in computational power have spurred numerous numerical investigations into passing ship phenomena. For instance, Huang and Chen (2006) utilized a Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) CFD approach to investigate the hydrodynamic effects on a passing ship as influenced by a nearby moored vessel and its mooring system. Highlighting contemporary efforts, Kwon and Yeon (2023) conducted a comprehensive CFD study using Simcenter STAR-CCM+ to analyze the interaction of a KCS container ship passing near two tankers moored in tandem, showcasing the application of modern CFD tools to complex multi-body scenarios.

3. Methodology

This section details the numerical methodology employed to investigate the hydrodynamic forces and moments acting on a vessel moored to buoys at various oblique angles relative to a navigation channel during the passage of another ship. To simulate these complex, unsteady, three-dimensional interactions, a numerical approach founded on Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) was adopted. This CFD approach utilizes the Finite Volume Method (FVM) to discretize and solve the governing Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) equations, as detailed below. A critical component for accurately modeling the large relative motions between the passing and moored vessels was the implementation of an overset mesh technique.

3.1. Problem Definition

This study investigates the hydrodynamic forces exerted on a moored tanker vessel due to the nearby passage of an Ultra-Large Container Vessel (ULCV). The core of the investigation focuses on understanding how these interactions are influenced when the moored tanker is oriented at various non-parallel (oblique) heading angles relative to the path of the passing ULCV.

The key vessels involved in the simulated scenarios are:

- Passing Vessel: An Ultra-Large Container Vessel (ULCV) with a length between perpendiculars (L_{pp}) of 366 m, a beam (B) of 52 m and draft (H) of 15.3m.
- Moored Vessel: A tanker with an L_{pp} of 175.5 m and a beam (B) of 40 m and draft (H) of 11.7m.

For each distinct simulation case within the parametric study, the moored tanker is set at a specific, fixed orientation. This initial orientation of the moored tanker defines the relative heading angle (θ) with respect to the consistent, straight trajectory of the passing ULCV. The passing ULCV itself transits at a constant forward speed of 7 knots (approximately 3.6 m/s) along this trajectory for all cases.

The primary parameters investigated are as follows. The *Relative Heading Angle* (θ) is defined as the angle between the longitudinal axis of the moored tanker and the trajectory of the passing ULCV with its origin at the stern of the ship. This angle was varied systematically from $\theta = 0^\circ$ (indicating the moored tanker is parallel to the ULCV's path) to $\theta = 90^\circ$ (indicating the moored tanker is perpendicular, or beam-on, to the ULCV's path). The *Lateral Separation Distance* (S_L) is defined as the perpendicular distance between the port side of the passing ULCV's and the starboard face of the moored tanker (measured at its midship). This distance was maintained at 205 m for all simulated cases.

The simulations were conducted assuming a finite water depth $H = 17.9$ m. The overall objective of simulating these defined problem scenarios is to accurately quantify the transient hydrodynamic forces surge and sway experienced by the moored tanker. This data is intended to provide a clearer understanding of the impact of non-parallel passing ship interactions, particularly concerning the influence of large vessels like ULCVs, which is essential for robust mooring system design and operational safety assessments within ports and harbors.

3.2. CFD Approach

To model the simulations, the commercial CFD software Simcenter STAR-CCM+ Siemens Digital Industries Software (2021) was used. This software consists of various packages of main solver submodels, such as turbulence model and interface-tracking model.

3.2.1. URANS

The governing equation for the problem is URANS equations written in an inertial fixed reference frame $(x_1, x_2, x_3) = (x, y, z)$. The Navier-Stokes equations of continuity and motion can be written for Newtonian fluids in incompressible flow:

$$\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\rho U_i U_j + \rho u_i \bar{u}_j) = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} [\mu (\partial U_i \partial x_j + \partial U_j \partial x_i)] + \rho B_i \quad (2)$$

Where U_i and U_j are the Reynolds-average velocity component in i and j direction, respectively; P is the pressure; ρ is density; μ is the dynamic viscosity; and ρB_i is the body forces. These equations are closed by modeling the correlation of $\bar{u}_i \bar{u}_j$ as the so-called Reynolds Stress Tensor $\tau_{ij} = \bar{u}_i \bar{u}_j$, a second-order symmetric tensor.

To predict the turbulence effects, a RANS turbulence model (TM) $k\omega - SST$ was used. This TM combines the strengths of the $k - \epsilon$ TM, which predicts reasonable the far field flows, and $k - \omega$, accurate to predict near walls. It introduces a blending function to switch between the far fields to the near wall (boundary layer). Menter (1994)

3.2.2. Overset Mesh Method

For moving body problems, Simcenter STAR-CCM+ has an overset mesh technique implemented. An overset mesh is a dynamic grid technique where multiple overlapping mesh regions (background and component meshes) are used to handle complex moving geometries, such as ships, propellers, or offshore structures. The background mesh covers the global domain, while finer component meshes surround moving objects, allowing them to move independently without mesh distortion. Interpolation zones (donor-receiver interfaces) exchange flow data between overlapping regions, ensuring accurate simulation of relative motion. This approach is particularly useful for marine applications, such as ship maneuvering or passing ships, where large displacements and complex interactions occur. Overset meshing reduces remeshing needs, improves computational efficiency, and maintains solution accuracy for moving-boundary problems. Pinkster (2004)

3.3. Domain and Boundary Conditions

The domain extents were carefully designed to ensure both physical accuracy and numerical stability, with the moored ship's length (L_{pp}) used as the reference length. The upstream length was set to $3.5 L_{pp}$ to allow proper flow development before reaching the vessel, while the downstream length extended to $7.7 L_{pp}$ to minimize reverse flow at the outlet. The scenario models the moored vessel anchored in open water, with no mooring quay or wall boundaries nearby. Consequently, lateral boundaries were positioned sufficiently far from the vessels ($\geq 2L_{pp}$) to eliminate confinement effects while enabling the use of symmetry conditions.

Figure 1: Sketch of the numerical domain used in the simulations

The computational domain employed the following boundary conditions to model the hydrodynamic interactions:

- **Inlet:** A *stagnation inlet* boundary condition was applied to prescribe the total pressure and flow direction, ensuring accurate mass flux while allowing the static pressure to adjust dynamically.
- **Outlet:** A *pressure outlet* condition with fixed static pressure was used to allow fluid to exit the domain while maintaining numerical stability.
- **Bottom:** Modeled as a *no-slip wall* to simulate the seabed or channel bottom, with zero velocity at the boundary (i.e., $u = 0$).
- **Sides:** Treated as *symmetry planes* to reduce computational cost, assuming negligible cross-flow effects in these directions.
- **Top:** The free surface was modeled using a double-body boundary condition, effectively simulating the water-air interface through a symmetry plane approximation. This approach is commonly employed for submerged body analyses where free surface deformation effects are secondary to the primary hydrodynamic interactions. (Pinkster (2004)).

3.4. Mesh Generation Details

The computational meshes for this study were generated using the integrated meshing capabilities of Simcenter STAR-CCM+, employing predominantly trimmed hexahedral cells. A multi-region overset mesh technique was adopted, comprising a stationary background domain and distinct moving overset regions for the moored tanker and the passing ULCV. The background mesh, encompassing the entire computational domain (as defined in Section 3.3.), gradually coarsening towards the far-field boundaries, and consisted

of approximately 4,256,000 cells. Separate overset meshes were generated around the hulls of the passing ULCV (approximately 3,308,597 cells) and the moored tanker (approximately 166,556 cells). These component meshes featured significantly finer resolution to accurately capture near-vessel flow details.

To further enhance resolution in areas of high gradients or critical flow phenomena, volumetric refinement zones were implemented immediately surrounding the ship hulls, in their anticipated wake regions, and along the overset interface to ensure smooth data transition. Critical for resolving viscous effects, prism layers were generated on all wetted hull surfaces. For the passing ULCV, this typically involved [e.g., $N_L = 10$ to 15] layers with a first layer thickness carefully controlled to achieve a target non-dimensional wall distance (y^+) of approximately 1, ensuring direct resolution of the viscous sublayer. A similar prism layer strategy, employing a geometric growth rate of 1.3, was applied to the moored tanker to model its boundary layer development. The overset interface between these component meshes and the background mesh was managed by Simcenter STAR-CCM+ using a distance weighted scheme for exchanging flow variables, with a sufficient overlap of at least 3 cells maintained between the meshes to ensure numerical stability and accurate data transfer. The total cell count for the simulations was approximately 7.73 million cells. Standard mesh quality metrics, such as cell skewness and aspect ratio, were monitored during generation and maintained within acceptable limits to ensure robust and accurate numerical solutions. 2 show the y-plane view of the passing ship and moored ship mesh.

(a) Y-plane of Moored Ship mesh

(b) Y-plane of passing ship mesh

Figure 2: Grids of 0 case.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Hydrodynamic Force Analysis

This section presents a detailed analysis of the time-dependent dimensionless hydrodynamic loads on the moored vessel across a full range of heading angles, from parallel (0°) to perpendicular (90°) relative to the passing ship's path.

As a crucial aspect of mooring analysis, the time series reveal that both surge and sway forces (Figures 3 and 4) exhibit complex, cyclical behavior with distinct phases of positive (repulsive) and negative (attractive/suction) forces. The time series for surge (Figure 3) shows that at low angles (0° to 30°), an initial repulsive force is dominant, followed by a significant attractive force. At higher angles, this behavior inverts, with the attractive force becoming the most prominent peak. Similarly, the sway force (Figure 4) is characterized by a primary repulsive peak across all angles, which is consistently followed by a notable suction (attractive) force.

An analysis of both positive and negative peak forces as a function of heading angle provides critical insights. For the surge force (Figure 5), the repulsive peak (positive) is dominant at low angles, reaching a maximum of nearly 0.8 at 10° before decreasing. Conversely, the magnitude of the attractive (suction) peak is smaller at low angles but grows steadily, surpassing the repulsive peak around 40° and reaching its

Figure 3: Surge force time series

Figure 4: Sway force time series

maximum magnitude of 1.0 at 90°. This clearly illustrates a shift in dominance from repulsive to attractive surge forces as the heading angle increases.

The sway force (Figure 6) presents an even more complex interaction. The repulsive peak (positive) behaves non-monotonically, with significant peaks at 10°, 30°, and 50°. Simultaneously, the attractive (suction) peak's magnitude shows a generally increasing trend with the angle, rising from less than 0.3 at 10° to nearly 1.0 at 90°. This demonstrates that while the peak repulsive sway force fluctuates, the peak suction force becomes an increasingly significant and predictable component of the load at higher heading angles, which is a critical consideration for mooring system design.

Figure 5: Maximum surge force coefficient vs. heading angle.

Figure 6: Maximum sway force coefficient vs. heading angle.

4.2. Flow Physics at Different Angles

To understand the physical mechanisms driving the peak forces, the pressure fields acting on the moored vessel were visualized at the precise instant of each maximum peak (repulsion and suction for both surge

and sway).

The peak repulsive surge forces (Figure 7) are generated by a high-pressure zone near the bow of the moored vessel, caused by the passing ship's own pressure field. This effect is most pronounced at low angles (0° to 30°), which directly corresponds to the higher repulsive peaks observed in the force graph (Figure 5). As the angle increases, this frontal pressure accumulation diminishes, leading to the decay in the repulsive surge force.

Conversely, the peak attractive surge forces (Figure 8) are dominated by a distinct low-pressure (suction) zone that forms near the stern of the moored vessel. At low angles, this suction zone is minor, but as the heading angle increases towards 90° , it becomes significantly more intense and covers a larger area. This visual evidence perfectly explains the trend seen in Figure 5, where the suction force magnitude grows steadily and becomes the dominant surge component at higher angles.

The analysis of the sway forces reveals a similar direct correlation. The peak repulsive sway forces (Figure 9) are caused by a strong pressure differential across the vessel, with a high-pressure area on the starboard (exposed) side and a low-pressure area on the port (leeward) side. The oscillatory behavior seen in the force graph (Figure 6) can be attributed to the complex and non-linear changes in the size, shape, and position of these pressure zones as the heading angle varies.

Finally, the peak attractive sway forces (Figure 10) are generated almost entirely by the low-pressure (suction) zone on the leeward side of the moored vessel. As the angle increases, this suction zone not only intensifies but also acts on a larger effective surface area perpendicular to the sway direction. This provides a clear physical explanation for the consistent and nearly linear growth of the sway suction magnitude seen in Figure 6.

Figure 7: Pressure contour fields at the instant of maximum repulsive surge force for each heading angle.

5. Conclusions

6. Conclusions

This study employed a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) methodology to investigate the hydrodynamic forces on a moored vessel during the passage of a ULCV at various non-parallel heading angles. The

Figure 8: Pressure contour fields at the instant of maximum attractive (suction) surge force for each heading angle.

Figure 9: Pressure contour fields at the instant of maximum repulsive sway force for each heading angle.

Figure 10: Pressure contour fields at the instant of maximum attractive (suction) sway force for each heading angle.

detailed analysis of the pressure fields at the moments of peak loading provided direct physical insight into the complex hydrodynamic phenomena.

The results revealed a clear transition in the dominant surge force, from repulsion driven by pressure build-up at the bow at low angles, to suction driven by a low-pressure zone at the stern at high angles. For the sway force, the analysis demonstrated that the oscillatory behavior of the repulsive peak is due to complex shifts in the pressure differential across the vessel, while the secondary attractive (suction) peak showed a clear trend of increasing magnitude, directly linked to the growth of the leeward-side low-pressure zone.

The findings underscore that mooring loads in non-parallel scenarios are defined by a shifting balance between four distinct loading mechanisms (repulsion and suction in both surge and sway), whose relative importance changes significantly with heading angle. A comprehensive mooring design must account for the full range and reversal of these loads. The growing significance of suction forces in both surge and sway at higher angles is a particularly critical takeaway for ensuring system robustness.

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